

DETERMINING THE EFFECT OF GROWTH-REGULATING SUBSTANCES ON ROOT DEVELOPMENT IN THE PROPAGATION OF KUMQUAT CUTTINGS

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Abstract. The research results showed that the application of indole-3-butyric acid (IBA) influenced leaf development in kumquat cuttings. When different concentrations were studied, the best leaf development was observed at IBA 50 mg/L, which achieved the highest показатели compared to the control variant.

Keywords: Kumquat, cutting, leaf, surface, indole-3-butyric acid (IBA), average area, assimilation surface, shoot.

With the continuous growth of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the demand for food—especially fruits and processed fruit products, as well as their variety and quality—is steadily increasing. In particular, it would not be an exaggeration to say that citrus fruits and their cultivation and processed products rank first in popularity among all fruit crops.

Citrus plants can be propagated both by seeds and vegetatively. Seed propagation is mainly used in rootstock production and breeding work, while varietal seedlings are produced through vegetative methods. Worldwide, citrus plants are primarily propagated vegetatively, especially by cuttings. Vegetative propagation refers to the regeneration of a new plant from a somatic part of the mother plant. In this case, the produced seedlings fully retain all the biological characteristics of the parent plant.

In the growth and development of propagated seedlings, leaf development plays an important role. It significantly influences plant respiration, shoot growth and development, as well as the degree of shoot maturation.

Research objective. The aim of this study was to investigate the morpho-biological characteristics of kumquat (*Fortunella japonica*) and to develop effective elements of intensive seedling production technology.

Research results. Growth-regulating substances play an important role in producing seedlings from cuttings of the Nagami kumquat variety. In determining the optimal concentrations of indole-3-butyric acid (IBA), the following results were obtained (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Determination of leaf development and leaf surface area in the propagation of Nagami kumquat cuttings.

In the untreated (control) variant of kumquat cuttings, the average number of leaves per shoot was 4, the average leaf area was 7 cm², and the total assimilation surface of leaves developed per seedling was found to be 0.28 m². Compared to the control variant, treatment with IBA at 30 mg/L resulted in the following outcomes:

Table.

Determining the effect of growth-regulating substances on leaf development in the propagation of Nagami kumquat cuttings.

Varieties	Average number of leaves per shoot (pcs)	Average leaf area (cm ²)	Assimilation surface of the seedling (m ²)
Nagami variety			
Untreated (control)	4	7	0,28
IBA 30 mg/L (water solution)	6	8	0,48
IBA 40 mg/L (water solution)cyB;	8	12	0,96
IBA 50 mg/L (water solution)	12	14,6	1,7
IBA 60 mg/L (water solution)	9	12	1,1

When treated with IBA, the average number of leaves per shoot increased by 2.0 compared to the control variant, while the average leaf area in the control variant was 1 cm² higher, and the seedling assimilation surface was 0.20 m² greater.

When treated with IBA at 40 mg/L, the average number of leaves per shoot increased by 4 compared to the control, the average leaf area was 5 cm² larger, and the assimilation surface of the seedling was 0.68 m² greater than in the control variant.

When treated with IBA at 50 mg/L, the average number of leaves per shoot was 8 higher than in the control, the average leaf area was 7.6 cm² higher, and the assimilation surface of the seedling was 1.4 m² greater.

When treated with IBA at 60 mg/L, the average number of leaves per shoot increased by 5 compared to the control, the average leaf area was 5 cm² higher, and the assimilation surface of the seedling was 1.9 m² higher than in the control variant (see table).

Based on the experimental results, it can be concluded that the application of IBA at an optimal concentration has a positive effect on the leaf coverage of Nagami kumquat plants. However, both lower and higher-than-optimal doses may negatively affect leaf growth and development.

Conclusion. For the growth and proper development of leaves in the Nagami kumquat variety, the optimal concentration of IBA was found to be 50 mg/L water. At this concentration, the leaf surface area was 1.5 m² higher than in the control variant.

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